

TEACHING ENGLISH GRAMMAR THROUGH EFFECTIVE APPROACHES AND METHODS

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ABSTRACT

The article deals with the specifics of various effective methods, their principles and techniques in teaching grammar to students of higher education.

Keywords: teaching English grammar, specific forms of the verb, categories of tense, type and pledge, principles and methods of teaching.

The greatest difficulty in teaching English grammar is represented by the modern forms of the verb. Students face difficulties in mastering grammatical forms of the verb. Most often, such problems arise due to a vague idea of the category of time, type and collateral. Therefore, it is necessary to consider methods and approaches in teaching English grammar, what problems arise for students of modern forms of the verb, what characteristic mistakes they make and what modern methods, techniques and exercises can eliminate these problems.

The use of supports at the stage of introduction and training of the modern English verb system facilitates the process of learning English for students, stimulates communication between students in foreign language lessons, focuses attention on new passable material and promotes the formation of strong skills and abilities.

The relevance of the work is due to the lack of development in terms of the selection of materials of the most effective methodological techniques aimed at eliminating the difficulties of using modern forms of the English verb in speech.

A foreign language is a language that is rarely used in the social environment closest to the student. It can be used in upcoming trips in the future or any other cross-cultural communication. It is studied as a compulsory subject or elective course, but without immediate practical application. In the matter of describing methods, the difference between the philosophy of language teaching at the level of theory and principles and a set of derived language teaching procedures is the main one. Accuracy in grammar is fundamental, and mistakes should be avoided at all costs. Activities in situational language learning continues to be part of the standard set of procedures approved by many modern methodologists. Textbooks written on the basis of situational language learning continue to be widely used round the world. But due to

the fact that the principles of situational learning the language, with their emphasis on oral practice, grammar and sentence structures are consistent with 217 by the intuition of many practice-oriented teachers, this method has remained widely popular [2].

Since structure is what is essential and important in the language, the initial practice should focus on mastering grammatical structures. Oral literacy implies the accuracy of pronunciation, grammar and the ability to respond quickly and accurately to speech situations. Learning listening, pronunciation, grammar and vocabulary relate to the development of fluency of speech. Reading and writing skills can also be taught, but they depend on the oral skills already available.

Language is speech, but the speaking skills themselves depend on the ability to accurately perceive and reproduce the main phonological features of the language being studied, on the fluency of using key grammatical structures and from the knowledge of the vocabulary volume sufficient for the use of these structures. The grammar of the English language has been subjected to intense discussion for many years. In the modern century, the role of grammar in teaching foreign languages has changed especially often: either increased or underestimated. In recent decades, there has been a tendency to reduce the role of grammar, which has led to a significant increase in the number of errors in the speech of students [1].

Grammars of foreign languages in many cases do not serve well to achieve practical learning goals. By itself, information about parts of speech, predicate types, and the like, as well as many tasks aimed at finding these grammatical phenomena in texts, at memorizing and reproducing them, does not contribute to the formation of speech skills, which are formed on the basis of specific mechanisms and are not related to the concepts and system established in linguistics. Vitlin J. L offers the conditions that he considers necessary for the successful achievement of the goal practical language proficiency:

1) it is necessary to strengthen differentiation in the selection of material for active and passive grammatical minima and when using (taking into account the peculiarities of the native language) different ways of teaching and learning to master these minima. The formulation of the rules of the active grammatical minimum should, in particular, show the usual ways of expressing thoughts in the native language by lexical and grammatical means. On the other hand, it is necessary to show students how to understand the grammatical forms that they encounter in foreign languages.

2) review the use of grammatical terminology in the course of the IA. To improve grammar teaching, it is advisable to create new textbooks for secondary schools, there the number of grammatical terms can be reduced to a certain minimum, and a short terminological dictionary with explanatory examples can be placed in textbooks.;

3) solve the problem of selecting grammatical phenomena in textbooks and programs for different types of educational institutions;

4) to change in many ways the traditional nature and language of the presentation of grammatical material when teaching students who do not have a linguistic education.

In modern conditions of teaching foreign languages, communicative and cognitive approaches are recognized as the leading approaches.

The communicative approach assumes a complete and optimal systematization of the relationships between the components of the learning content. These include: system of general activity; system of speech activity; system of speech communication; system of the English language itself; conscious comparative analysis of native and English languages; system of speech mechanisms (speech generation, speech perception, speech interaction, etc.); text as a system of speech products; a system of structural speech formations (dialogue, monologue, monologue in dialogue, different types of speech utterances and messages, etc.); a system of mastering the English language; a system of human speech behavior. As a result of this approach, a system of English language proficiency as a means of communication in the broad sense of the word is formed, implemented and operates in teaching [3].

The cognitive approach to grammar teaching helps the teacher to stimulate cognitive mechanisms of trainees, organize their independent reflexive activity, thanks to which comparative analysis, understanding, memorization, assignment and adequate use of grammatical structures in speech are provided [6].

At the same time, it is impossible to use traditional grammatical exercises. The main points are as follows:

- when working with grammar within the framework of the cognitive approach, the requirements for text material are significantly increased, which should provide students with a rich base for observing the functioning of the studied linguistic phenomenon and the establishment of patterns of its functioning;
- the task of the teacher is to widely use the whole range of cognitive strategies in the lesson and to stimulate the reflective activity of students;
- a system of exercises that ensures the improvement of the mechanisms of conceptualization of the studied facts of the language and the development of strategies for constructing a grammatical concept should be organized taking into account the stages that a person goes through on the path of cognition and appropriation of new knowledge [4].

Summing up, it should be noted that for many years the grammar of English language is one of the main aspects of language that has been subject to intense discussion. There are several approaches to teaching foreign languages.

Traditionally, methodologists distinguish explicit and implicit approaches. In modern conditions, teaching foreign languages, the leading approaches are recognized as communicative and cognitive approaches that stimulate the cognitive mechanisms of students, the organization of independent reflexive activity, thanks to which effective assimilation and adequate use of grammatical structures of a foreign language in speech is ensured.

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